

TECHNOLOGY AND GADGETS: BOON OR CURSE

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ABSTRACT

Technology has become so synonymous to all our lives today that we have even crossed that stage when we discussed whether it is a boon or bane. We live in the world where the impact of technology is huge. We use electronic gadgets in our daily life as an undifferentiated part of it. For example, cell phone, i-pad, tablet, laptop, computer etc. This field is full of innovations and continuous upgradation. These gadgets have drastically change the way of communication, entertainment, the quality of living etc. As we all know, every innovation has its own advantage and disadvantage. Having a smart phone is like, a whole world in our hand. We use these mobiles not only for requirements but for texting, visiting social networking sites, gaming, listening songs etc.

Continuous use of gadgets makes us addictive which causes not only physical but mental health problems also. For example, eye damage, obesity, muscular pain, many mental problems and certain type of cancer due to emission of radiofrequency energy (radio waves), a form of non-ionizing radiation, from their antennas. There is a specific absorption rate (SAR) of a mobile which is an indication of the amount of radiation that is absorbed into a head when we are using a mobile phone. WHO classified mobile devices as a group 2B risk, which means that they have the potential to be carcinogenic. Children, young people and pregnant women might be more at risk.

We are so busy in our virtual world that either we don't know or we don't care about what is going on around. So still the question is the same: Electronic gadgets a Boon or Curse? The answer is it depends upon how we use them. Gadgets are boon if we use them appropriately and can be curse if we don't use them properly.

Keywords: Gadgets, technology, electronic, virtual, cellphone, SAR, carcinogenic.

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INTRODUCTION

Throughout human history, technology has had a profound effect on human development and on the progress of civilization. Yet in no other time in history has technology been as pervasive in human lives as it is today. The rate of technological progress and society's dependence on technology only promises to intensify as the world moves into the twenty-first century. Technology can be defined as all the knowledge, products, processes, tools, methods and systems employed in the creation of goods or in providing services. In simple terms, technology is the way we do things. It is the means by which we accomplish objectives. We currently live in what truly can be termed the "knowledge age". Technology is knowledge applied to the creation purpose; but on a negative note, it can also be applied for destructive purposes. Technology today is an integral part of our everyday life. Rapid advancements in the field has increased the pace of life, effectively coordinating reality with imagination. In other words we virtually move with our thought and as we look ahead, today's technology becomes out dated tomorrow. Technology has become so synonymous to all our lives today that we have even crossed that stage when we discussed whether it is a boon or curse. Technology gave us so many products like electronic gadgets which we use in our daily life as an undifferentiated part of it. These electronic gadgets are as follows:-

- Cell phones
- Desktop computers
- Laptop computers
- Mp3 player
- Game consoles
- e-book reader
- Tablet computers

Services: Internet

The internet is a huge network that links

computers together all over the world using a range of wires and wireless technologies. The World Wide Web is the collection of linked pages those are accessed using the internet and a web browser. The purpose of using internet are online shopping, social networking, games, news, travel information, business, advertising and much more. One of the best common ways of finding information on the web is through the search engines like Google. Currently the most popular search engine is Google, which is receiving hundreds of millions of search queries in a day. A social networking service is a platform to build social networks or social relations among people who, for example, share interests, activities, backgrounds, or real-life connections. Social networking sites allow users to share ideas, pictures, posts, activities, events, and interests with people in their networks.

This field is full of innovations and continuous upgradation. These gadgets have drastically changed the way of communication, entertainment, the quality of living etc. Having a smart phone is like, we have a whole world in our hand.

Advantages of gadgets

Day by day mobile phones are becoming the essential part of our life. Check the ten benefits of cell phones:

1. Stay connected anytime and anywhere: The most basic benefit of a cell phone for which most of us use it is that we can stay connected with our loved ones in any part of the world and anytime. Gone are the days when we used to stand in queues to make an STD or ISD calls. You can talk to your loved ones staying even seven seas far with cell phones.
2. SMS: When initially SMS was invented, the makers were not actually sure whether it will work. But to their surprise SMSs are today the most widely used service across the world.
3. Your way out in emergencies: Imagine you

are stuck in a traffic jam, getting late for a meeting or your car has broken down in middle of nowhere. Cell phones are of great use in time of such emergencies. You can contact help with the use of cell phone easily.

4. Navigation in your hand: cell phones are constantly being upgraded with new technology and the recent phones are equipped with navigation and GPRS systems.
5. Mini PC: cell phones are nowadays almost equivalent to mini computers. The latest ones are equipped with windows and internet facilities. We can simply access the internet on our cell phone and get to know about the latest news, our e-mails, movie shows and a lot more!
6. Enhance your business: cell phones are a great help even at our business. With cell phones, we can constantly stay in touch with our employees and get to know about crucial information of our business.
7. Help in legal matters: a lot of criminals are these days being held because of their cell phones! The police can track a criminal via tracking the place where his mobile phone is using GPS. Also checking a cell phone's call records give vital information to the defense forces about the criminals.
8. Wholesome entertainment: with a cell phone in our hand, we don't need a TV or PC to get entertained. It is all in our cell phone. We can play games, listen to music, and click pictures and even record videos in our cell phone.
9. Transfer of data: these days cell phones are equipped with infrared and bluetooth technologies which allow us to transfer data like mails, pictures, music and even videos just in span of seconds.
10. Prestige and fashion statement: cell phones have become a matter of prestige and

fashion statement, especially among the youth

These all are benefits of smart phones. But this is not true for all. We are so busy in our virtual world that either we don't know or we don't care about what is going on around. As we know every coin has two phase positive and negative, electronic gadgets also have their dark phase. Students and kids are the biggest victim of gadgets.

Disadvantages of gadgets Negative effects on children

Children born today are technology savvy almost right at birth. Kids as young as 18 to 24 months use mobiles and tabs with great ease. Though they learn a couple of things there too but overuse of it can lead to some behavioral issues like Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Restlessness and Aggression.

Researchers have found that the negative impacts of gadgets and electronic media outweigh the positive. Some of the significant impacts of gadgets on children's brain development and behavior are as follows:

1. **Not good for the brain:** Overexposure to gadgets has been linked to Attention Deficit, Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), cognitive delays and impaired learning.
2. **Language delay for toddlers:** According to American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP), severe language delay is seen in children who are overexposed to gadgets.
3. **Less active play equals delayed development:** Kids under the age of 12 spend more time in front of a screen rather than playing outdoors. This restriction in movement results in delayed motor development.
4. **Not good for bedtime:** The late-night glow of laptops and mobile phones are depriving children a good night sleep.

5. **Not good for school:** Being sleep-deprived doesn't only affect child development but also their performance in school.
6. **Terrible child aggression:** A study by the National Institutes of Health found that the increase in use of modern technology can break the old boundaries of family, values, behavior and children's well-being.
7. **Kids suffer mental illness:** A study of more than 1,000 children between the ages of 10 and 11, found that children who spend longer than two hours in front of a screen or another entertainment medium are more likely to suffer psychological difficulties.
8. **Gadgets cause tantrums:** Kids throw tantrums because they get over attached to gadgets and can't emotionally handle themselves when these devices are taken away from them.

Other negative effects of gadgets

Continuous use of gadgets makes us addictive which causes not only physical but mental health problems also. Few of them are given below:

- 1) The back lit screen of computers, laptops, mobiles and tablets causes eye damage.
- 2) Decrease the liking towards exercise which leads to obesity. The obesity may lead to other serious health problems.
- 3) Excess use of gadgets make us mentally sick. We may have mental problems like Anxiety, depression, obsessive compulsive disorder, bipolar disorder.
- 4) Swelling and pain due to excess touch with thumb and index finger.
- 5) Continuous use of gadgets is the reason for back pain, neck pain, shoulder pain.
- 6) Cell phones might have the potential to cause certain type of cancer.

Mobile phone radiations

Cell phones emit radiofrequency energy (radio

waves), a form of non-ionizing radiation, from their antennas. Non-ionizing radiation refers to a variety of electronic radiation. In the simplest terms, this means that non-ionizing radiation only excites matter into another form of energy. It does not ionize molecules which can cause more harmful radiation effects. There is a specific absorption rate (SAR) of a mobile which is an indication of the amount of radiation that is absorbed into a head when we are using a mobile phone.

The World Health Organization (WHO) announced on May 31, 2011 that mobile phones emit enough radiation to add it to the same carcinogenic list as exhaust from engines and lead. For years, the WHO assured mobile phone users that there were no significant risks from repeated use.

What does the WHO's declaration mean?

It took 31 scientists from around the world. This study involved 14 countries and was released by the International Agency for Research on Cancer. They have deemed mobile phone use to have a possible cancer risk to humans similar to that of using a microwave in the home. So far, scientists have determined only two types of Cancer that directly correlate with these results. These two Cancers are: Glioma and Acoustic Neuromas. Since mobile phones are still a relatively new technology development in the last 25 years, it may take many more studies in the coming years to provide more reliable data.

How mobile affects our brain?

The WHO has determined that mobile phones emit the same type of radiation microwaves do. When using a microwave, you heat up whatever you happen to place in it. This is similar to what happens to your brain when you are exposed to non-ionizing radiation.

The National Institute of Health released a study in February 2011 that showed just 50 minutes of continued mobile phone usage caused an increase in brain cell activity. This stimulation is still being looked to as far as long-term effects on the human

brain. It will take more research and time to find the effects of mobile phone usage and how it may cause Cancer.

Do we have to stop using our mobile phone?

These devices have become almost inseparable from us during the day. Can we even imagine living without a mobile phone in today's world? Most of us cannot. If we are not talking to family, we are texting friends or emailing coworkers. Mobile phones have become an integral part of our lives. Every year providers release new devices, increase the speed data can travel through the air and make these mobile phones more desirable for consumers all over the world.

Does this latest study from the World Health Organization mean we have to stop using our phones? Are we in danger of developing Cancer and other harmful effects from using them? Should we stop using our mobile phone? Probably not.

Should we more aware of what using our phone can do to our health? Definitely. While technology seems to evolve at the speed of light, the answers to these questions will take much more time than we are used to waiting in today's age.

As parents, we can practice a few things to prevent your kid from being enslaved to technology. Here are a few tips:

1. **De-addict yourself:** Kids always grow on the model of imitation. When they see their parents glued to their mobiles, they also develop a strong desire to explore the same. Limiting the use of mobile and tab in front of kids can go a long way in dissuading away from them.
2. **Sing, act, dance:** Bond with your child by singing those rhymes that he enjoys watching on the tab. Sing those rhymes, stand up and act and dance.
3. **Read books together:** Invest in some interesting story books with big and colorful

pictures. Not only would it help develop reading habit in the kid, will build his language skills and cognitive development as well.

4. **Play interactive games:** Encourage him/her for interactive and outdoor games that would lead to his/her social and physical development.
5. **Restricted screen time:** If you are busy with some house or office work and want to seek refuge in the digital medium to engage your toddler, allow access only for a limited time period.

Last but not the least; don't worry about keeping your child away from gadgets until he/she is five. It will not make your child any less gadget-savvy when he/she grows up. It will still come naturally to this generation as they are born after the advent of gadgets.

So, in the end still the question is the same: Electronic Gadgets a Boon or Curse? The answer is it depends upon how we use them. Gadgets are boon if we use them appropriately and they can be a curse as shown above if we don't use them properly.

FURTHER READINGS

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